

Original Research Paper

BONE TERATOGENICITY AN IN DEPTH ANALYSIS WITH APPLICATION OF MORPHOMETRY AFTER NANOSILVER COLLOID ORAL REPEAT GAVAGES TO PARA SWISS ALBINO MICE OF EXPERIMENTAL AND NORMAL GROUP

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ABSTRACT

Nanosilver maintain its absolute importance in global business field because of its burn induced scar healing nature, non steroidal anti hypertrophy and to some extent analgesic property. It boost's bone mineralization activity along with active transportation of nutrition towards Volkmann's canal along with this it also strongly induces growth of embryological woven bone very firstly to reach its maturity in medulla of bone which is right now a major cause of global research among scientific community. Apart from this it also possesses antifungal, antibacterial and injury induced wound convalescence activity. This nanometal mesmerizes the scientific community when a hidden fact is discovered that it releases a single silver molecule into bacterial cell core. After in depth analysis the meticulous research related to this area came to a conclusion that Nanosilver particulate in higher dose and larger size causes bonny teratogenicity, newly forming bone degrowth which is irregular and half hazard and so also the repeated oral ingestion of it causes severe malformations in F1 generation embryo that in in-vitro aspect of model mother and neonate animal. 1936nm to 24nm size range nanosilver colloid solution was induced in form of repeated oral gavages to Para Swiss Albino model mother animal at a higher dose of (8, 16, 24, 32 mg/kg b.w.). The normal group mother receive vehicle as normal saline in form of repeated oral gavages). Newborn Fetuses were collected on day 19th of gestation by ventral laparotomy. Alcian Red along with KOH staining were superimposed upon New born fetuses to validate bonny malformation. The common bonny malformations seen were no ossified long, flat and irregular bones. Specific bonny malformations seen were breech, kyphosis, duplication irregularity of vertebrae and hypo plastic and atrophied bone deformity.

Keywords: Spina Bifida, Open and close type NTD, Bone dressing, Yank

INTRODUCTION

Fabric industry, Drug industry, Consumer utilized product industry have spread the use of nano silver so widely. Several of skeletal system teratogenic effects are commenced due to this small and large size nanosilver and titanium oxide nanoparticulates from which one of the most vital biological living products is human and mice who genuinely suffer from skeletal dysmorphology. The exploration of the recent facts could be analyzed with the stanza from same research datas ¹. The data indicates that there are certain

biochemical tools and pharmaceutical drugs which can influences teratogenic episodes on the contrary nanosilver and titanium oxide and aluminium oxide nanoparticulate induces bony malformation in loading high dose oral gavages schedule experiment on offspring of pregnant Swiss Albino mice. After oral ingestion nanosilver colloid solution in course of oral gavages experiment; In due course of development this nanosilver and titanium oxide nanoparticulate enhances major drug induced malformations of various body internal systems of fetuses which is also observed in hi-

tect countries like Germany and England about 6 to 7% and in developing countries like Pakistan, Ghana etc about 23 to 32%.^{2,3} Past data on *in-vitro* risk evaluation reported nanosilver transmigration which causes decreased cell penetration, damage of cell membrane and other micro anatomical destructive effects. Several other old data's also proposed nanosilver and titanium and aluminium nanoparticle to be most toxogenic among all metal nanoparticulate.⁴⁻⁶ A detrimental state of average level is observed when HILA-60 cell grow on metal silver plate. Some scientists saw accumulation of nano silver and titanium and aluminium nanoparticulates over cell surface on cells experiment⁷⁻¹¹ and find that highest deposit with large size deposit can be cytodetrimental in rat liver cell and Mammalian germ line stem cells.¹² This present and latest research activity also sparkles the recent global about corrosive and detrimental consequence of argentum nanometal on framework system of body. Retrospectively Swiss albino mice fetuses through repeated oral gavages experiment was undertaken on strong emphasis to calculate & reformat those lists of skeletal malformations consequence so called framework system disambiguation of the body of newly born fetuses. All over the global nanotechnologies are utilized on peak basis to create new consumer products, or these latest global nanotechnologies are confined to be used, to advance technical aura of food item regeneration. Including food prepared from silvernano-accessories and its direct involvement to improve desirable mentality in part of manufacture, utility and its storage. This attribute, governed by Food Standards Australia New Zealand (FSANZ), interrogates the scientific creative writing to decide whether there is currently objective evidence for determining if adverse skeletal system defects may be associated with argentums nano-forms of insoluble inorganic food additives. This teratogenic research study explains such bigger size silvernano-particulates as engineered nanosubstances (ENSs). Basically an ENS is defined as a nanosubstance with at least one confirmatory size less than 70nm. This ongoing research study is primarily concerned with whether the large size ENS negotiated offbeat idiosyncrasy to the food additive that result in demonstrably different health risks relative to the same food supplement used in large size-nano (i.e. extent quantity) form which especially affect skeletal system. The demeanor in which skeletal system risk of a body conceivably combine with nanotechnology applications in the cuisine zone is regulated by international food regulatory authorities. (IFRA) This ongoing research study contributes a compendium abstract of the absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) of silvernano particulates. The insolence, deviation and biodistracton

of ENSs after ingestion are restrained by probable deterioration and/or volatilization during passage through the GIT, or by food in the GIT. ENSs may also aggregate to larger sizes and as a result be excreted without being absorbed into the body. Nano-specific properties of an ENS are linked to the physical rectitude of the constituting nano-structure. When an ENS loses its nano-structure, it affects skeletal system of body.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The ongoing research study is conducted, for the purpose of demonstrating various skeletal malformations due to repeated ingestion of large size silvernano in colloidal solution form in gavages which is approved by Central Animal Ethical Committee BHU. 37 female Swiss albino mice with an average age 55 days and 32 to 37 gm weight were selected desultorily from Animal house, from different development provinces. These females were indulged sexual intercourse by male mouse of same race willfully with an objective for getting 15 offspring's of F2 generation. In the elastic pollinate enclosure with exemplary brace garnish single strong and robust heterozygous male mouse of same variety were placed with single female mouse in an atmosphere continuously maintained at 21-27°C and 57±7% humidity, 12hrs subsequently light and dark cycle. The female mice were examined for vaginal cross plug and presence of well visualize plug were marked as ascertained pregnancy and assigned day zero of gestational. On day 9, 10 and 11 of gestation plugged females were chequed for pregnancy by abdominal palpation.

Successful Characterization of Bigger Size AgNps

Nano silver particulates avail from investigation acquiring origin were assessed for their priliminary size by Transmission Electron Microscope and for their heaping in cell medium by photon cross correlation spectroscopy (PCCS) and ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy, Dynamic light Scattering (DLS) and Zeta potential. Counselor Transmission Electron Microscopy impressions of the nanosilver were displayed. The Transmission Electron Microscopy images of the poly vinyl pyrrolidone laminated AgNps diffuse and dangling in 1.54M Sodium chloride solution proved the preliminary particulate size and shape demonstrated by the operators. The unlaminated nanosilver particulates found amalgamate dissemination within the range of 70 to 125 nm, most of them being around 97nm.

In the case of dangling powder nanosilver, Transmission Electron Microscope impressions exhibited that in an aqueous environment the Ag nano particulate clustering and form giant agglomeration, many of which are huge than 65 nm. This consequence is in persistent with the results of aerodynamic diameter dissemination which was retrieved from the DLS method (zita sized). Energy

Dispersive X-Ray spectroscopy analysis for Elemental Composition of Material (EDAX) settled that only elementary Ag was conferred in both colloidal and dusty grate AgNps. As per Optical Emission Spectrometer Direct Analysis under 20 sec decisions, the consolidations of silver ions in the blotter absorbed or dissolved equips of colloidal and drooping crumb AgNps were 1936.23 and 466.28mg/l respectively where lowest is 24.37nm. Also decisions of the X-Ray Diffraction pattern affirms the cross pollinity of dusty type AgNps and presence of elementary cross pollinity silver, also other aspects, lacking alloyic Ag, were not present in the sample. With addendum to the X-Ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy decision demonstrated that cleanliness of dusty type nanosilver was 98.45%.

Disclosure of Nano Ag colloidal solution through imitated sonant boluses

Full pregnable murine mother animal (Swiss Albino Mice Of C57BL/6 And BALB/c strain) were orally administered two times with orderly briny (normal saline) (Sham control) as automobile and in a dose of 8, 16, 24, 32 mg/kg b.w. were given through imitated sonant boluses, from 6 to 13 gestational day with the help of a round edge arched handle bolster bait and caravan fixed. Orally administered two times with orderly briny murine animals are combined in this scientific experiment with served murine animals and unserved murine animals.

Postmortem and Obsecration

Material

On Gestational Day 19, both snouts of uterus of pregnable murine mother animal were exemplify following ventral laparotomy under ocean brine ether/chloroform analgesic insentience and 327 fresh collected dams through Post Mortem were scrubbed with tap water on Petri dish. Blood and amniotic fluid stain were removed by gentle rub. Samples were dehydrated and dessicated by filter paper and dry out in 100% alcohol for 72hrs at the end uncovered to one percent Pottasium Hydroxide for consistence Obsecration and Alizarin blemishing covenant for appropriate eye of the mind of osseins and bony process either orderly or nonorderly.¹³

Method (Appraisal of Bone Teratogenicity by Obsecration and Alizarin blemishing covenant):-

Bone Teratogenicity research study was conducted by the technique of obsecration and Alizarin Alizarin blemishing covenant. All specimens (65 pups) from each

group were dehydrated in 100% of alcohol (rectified spirit) for 72 hours and then removed and scrubbed by running tap water and then obscerated by one percent Potassium Hydroxide solution (Potassium Hydroxide 1.2 gm+102ml distilled water). After conduction of ventral laparotomic excision of abdominal wall (fully exposed) all soft viscera's are removed. The specimens were dipped fully in plenty of 1% KOH solution for at least 3 to 5 days until the flesh, tendon, muscles and soft viscera's were transparent & clear. They were seen demobilizing persue by clear cut limpid visible clarity of the hard skeleton and soft skeleton. Dipped solutions are changed every day when the solution become defile and dissipates.

The demobilizing hard and soft skeleton clear cut visible specimens were again dipped in same previous one percent Potassium Hydroxide and then 9 to 11 drops of one percent Alizarin stain was added to it to make it deep purple red color. Formal shaking of the same solution was done few times in every one hour interval. Then the same procedure was repeated for next 3-4 days in order to make it deep purple red color to hard and soft skeletons. As a precaution removal of over staining and over smoothness of the samples, the same are then passed through 50%, 90% (50ml glycerol+50ml distilled water, 90ml glycerol+10ml distilled water) and 2 to 3 bid of Thymol clear added for preservation of delicate specimens up to long time. Finally maintained in 100% pure glycerol and then set on experiment table for high resolution pixel photograph & powerful hand lens is used for critical surveillance of bone teratogenicity. Bone teratogenicity surveillance had been conducted on 327 offspring's of 37 mother murine animal. 60 offspring's were denoted stopped growth and absorbed.

Statistics

Rate of bone teratogenicity was calculated from each control treated group and evaluated for number of skeleton involved in the malformation and finally the rate and percentage percentages were compared in between the group and within the group for dose dependant teratogenicity factor. Multi Analysis Of Variance and Descriptive statistics (post hoc analysis) is applied.

Remark and Data Conclusions

The rate of bone teratogenicity was found higher and highest in 24mg AgNps and 32mg AgNps/ kg b.w. treated group pups (Table 1).

Groups	Number of Parous Murine Mice Used Per Group	of Fetuses Examined	No. of Offspring's With Bone Deformity		
			Fetuses found bone teratogenic	Several Teratogenicity Seen	Bone
32mg AgNp	5th	65	51(78.46%)	Excessive stage	of Spina

s/kg treated group	b.w.			Bifida, Open and close type NTD, Bone dressing, Yank, Forward bending of lumbar region, non ossified skull bones and face bones, Excess intercostals spaces and irregularity of thorax bones and cartilages, Fibrosed bones, gap in multiple weight bearing joints, irregular ribs, mandibulo facial dysostosis.
24 mg AgNPs/kg treated group	b.w.4th	65	37(56.92%)	Cervical vertebrae malformed and even absent, 12th rib completely absent, backward and regressive growth of spinous processes, Excessive gap in metatarsal bones, non-ossified spinous process, non-ossified pectoral girdle & pelvic girdle, , Forward bending of Lumbar Vertebraes, Absentia of soft chondrous part of all rib bones. Lumbar , sacral vertebrae and hip bone are either absent or malformed, moderate disambiguation of chest bone without cartilages, Regressive growth of skull and pelvic girdle, Forward bending, Dysostosis of Maxilla Bone, Incomplete closure of coronal and sagittal sutures, regressive growth of lower limb bone bilaterally.
16 mg AgNPs/kg treated group	b.w.3rd	65	27(41.53%)	Non-ossified 5th sternebrae segment from sternal bar, Non-ossified manubrium, Gap in sternum, Regression Of Maxillae and Mandible, Non-ossified Skull parts.
8 mg AgNPs/kg b.w. treated2nd group		65	16(24.61%)	

Table: 1 Multiple bone teratogenicity observed among the off springs of 32, 24, 16, 8 mg/kg b.w. AgNps treated groups Control group exhibited absolutely no symptoms.

8 mg AgNps/ kg b.w. treated group offspring's exhibited Non-ossified 5th sternbrae segment from sternal bar, Non-ossified manubrium, Gap in sternum, Regression Of Maxillae and Mandible, Non-ossified Skull parts. The percentage of bone teratogenicity calculated in this group was 24.61%.

The 16mg AgNps treated group exhibited Lumbar , sacral vertebrae and hip bone are either absent or malformed, moderate disambiguation of chest bone without cartilages, Regressive growth of skull and pelvic girdle, Forward bending, Dysostosis of Maxilla Bone, Incomplete closure of coronal and sagittal sutures, regressive growth of lower limb bone bilaterally. The percentage of bone teratogenicity calculated in this group was 41.53%.

24 mg/kg b.w. AgNps treated group offspring's were exhibited Cervical vertebrae malformed and even absent, 12th rib completely absent, backward and regressive growth of spinous processes, Excessive gap in metatarsal bones, non-ossified spinous process, non-ossified pectoral girdle & pelvic girdle , Forward bending of Lumbar Vertebraes, Absentia of soft chondrous part of all rib bones.

Lumbar , sacral vertebrae and hip bone are either absent or malformed, moderate disambiguation of chest bone without cartilages, Regressive growth of skull and pelvic girdle, Forward bending, Dysostosis of Maxilla Bone, Incomplete closure of coronal and sagittal sutures, regressive growth of lower limb bone bilaterally. The percentage of bone teratogenicity calculated in this group was 56.92%.

The 32mg/ kg b.w. AgNps treated group fetuses were exhibited highest percentage of bone teratogenicity (78.46%). Excessive stage of Spina Bifida, Open and close type NTD, Bone dressing, Yank, Forward bending of lumbar region, non ossified skull bones and face bones, Excess intercostals spaces and irregularity of thorax bones and cartilages, Fibrosed bones, gap in multiple weight bearing joints, irregular ribs, mandibulo facial dysostosis.

DISCUSSION

The existing teratogenic research work was undertaken to go through detail the detrimental effect of fetus before delivery. And AgNps colloidal solution exposure at this stage through repeated oral boluses on newly emerging skeleton of murine animal Swiss Albino mice embryos. The bone teratogenicity clash in this study were in the form of non-ossified skull bones and Spina Bifida, Open and close type NTD, Bone dressing, Yank, Forward bending of lumbar region, non ossified skull bones and face bones, Excess intercostals spaces and irregularity of thorax bones and cartilages, Fibrosed bones, gap in

multiple weight bearing joints, irregular ribs, mandibulo facial dysostosis. As observed by the groups 8mg, 16mg, 24mg, 32mg/kg b.w. facial skeleton and nasal cartilages hypo plasticity, forward bending, gap, complete non presence of parts of pelvic girdle, non fusion of parts of vertebrae and large cases of enlarged inter rib spaces and other chest bone deficits are encountered during the course of research laboratory work conducted in this existing study. As an astonishing result it has been observed that Alizarin bleaching covenant was not able to arrive up to tail region of murine animal offspring's. Though vast data are available among smaller dose Ag Nano toxicity from multiples company manufactured products, this existing study focuses on bone teratogenicity of murine animal offspring's of Swiss albino mouse variety which is dominant among several type of teratogenicities accomplished till date.

Ag Nano exhibits adversary characters in smallest dose that is antibacterial and hygienic characters (0.27-1.02 mg AgNps / kg b.w.) through skin application but astonishingly it exhibits bone teratogenic repercussion in 8, 16, 24, 32mg AgNps/ kg b.w. dose and toxicity repercussion in 0.56 & 1.07 mg/kg b.w. dose through repeated oral boluses application as per studies by Ema, Ema, M et al 2017; Tortella, G. R. et al 2020 and Clemente, Z. et al 2014 propounded that Titanium oxide Nanoparticulates and silver nanoparticles induces developmental toxicity in a few in vivo systems, most in aquatic and soil-related organisms and also reveals an interesting question arises from this experiment till date which is become a challenge to all nanoscientists of world to solve that is why toxicity in lower dose as teratogenicity in higher dose? ⁽¹⁴⁻¹⁶⁾ Charles S. et al. 2018; Rodriguez- Garrus A. et al. 2020; Guo X et al. 2016 & Li Y et al. 2017 systematically reviewed in vitro genotoxicity and teratogenicity data for Titanium Oxide Nanoparticles, yet it remained difficult to determine which inherent physicochemical properties (i.e., crystalline form, particle size, and/or surface coating) may explain the reasons for the diverging results observed. The mutagenicity and DNA damage produced by AgNPs and TiO₂ NPs and has been reported before using different in vitro assays and the effect of coating and size on the genotoxicity and teratogenicity of varied AgNPs and TiO₂ NPs and potential mechanisms have been discussed. ⁽¹⁷⁻²⁰⁾ In past research work conducted by same acknowledge auxiliary intense and long haul disclosure of Ag Nano initiates hypertrophy of inner tracheal lining or inside toxic focus. There is no prolonging effect in persistent alteration of Ag Nano into other organs. Even if more than sufficient nanoteratogenic research activities has been conducted

on chordate animals to demonstrate nanosilver osteo teratogenicity still there is something lacuna or breach in appropriate data available till date to show bone teratogenicity effect of multiple oral bolus experiment of synthesized nanosilver compound during prenatal to natal period which evokes malnutriated teratogenic effect like infertility, IUGR and other developmental anomalies among which osteo detrementation is demandable. Grodzik et al. 2006, Patel S et al. 2018, Egloff C. et al. 2011 & Chwalibog A et al. 2014 used the chick embryo model, the embryological anomaly (omphaloenterocele and flexed limbs) and interference in canonical Wnt signaling teratogenicity were found after serial ingestion of TiO₂ NPs (87.7 nm) ingestion at low doses only (10 and 25 µg/mL), while the inhibition on blood vessel formation and the abnormal lymph follicles in the bursa of Fabricius were reported after AgNPs exposure. The chicken embryo model can provide fast and precise assessment in developmental effects, tissue morphology, and gene expression level related to lipid metabolism and hormone homeostasis. They also performed an cumbersome nanosilver experiment on parous cytomegalous apes in which he induced nanosilver solution through external genitalia to internal part of uterus, he induced 1.5% AgNO₃ solution in period of 3rd to 6 weeks of prenatum and amazingly it cause per vaginal bleeding in prime period of induction and he also observed mechanical abortion of sustained pregnancy but as an adverse sequel of same nanosilver compound he also observed another pregnant lady of this particular experimentation gave rebirth to a strong and stout normal baby after getting pregnant.⁽²¹⁻²⁴⁾ Ghimire S et al. in 2022 conducted multiple scientific experiments. In which various toxicity endpoints have been reported by different nanoparticles in chick embryos, including embryotoxicity and teratogenicity, antiangiogenic or pro-angiogenic activity, neurotoxicity, and brain damage even the scientific experiment done by the same scientists concluded a abnormality of system defined Blue disease due to repeated and part by part, ingestion of total 6 to 7 gm AgNO₃ crystal within 6 month back experiment.⁽²⁵⁾ Rodriguez Garrus A et al. in 2020 reported the mutagenicity and DNA damage with teratogenicity produced by large size AgNPs has been documented before using different in vitro assays, he also conducted an illegal scientific experiment on old aged laborer by dusting silver powder on his cornea and sclera and larynx & he observed irritation of larynx and he also observed reduction in power to see in night in that old aged laborer.⁽¹⁸⁾ The oxidative stress has been observed as a contributor of the mutagenicity in the Ames test after TiO₂ NPs exposure. The mechanism of mutagenicity induced by NPs could be the result of two factors: one is the size-dependent internalization of the

particles and the other is the generation of oxidative stress by the catalytic potential of the particles. In the case of TiO₂ NPs, because their agglomerated forms exceeded the nano-scale size, the generation of oxidative stress from the NPs contributed mainly to the observed toxicity. Moss et al.²¹ also conducted the same critical illegal experiment and observed almost same to same complications. The extent of such silver powder exposure over those banned area fractioned in both experiment was 1 to 2 year in first experiment and 10 to 12 years in second experiment. Another same illegal experiment was carried out by Moss et al.²¹ by exposing AgNO₃ powder through nasal pathway by inspiration in factory workers in which he observed abnormal coloration of the parts of the parts of the eye ball of the exposure person. William²² also did the same illegal critical experiment and observed the same.^(26, 17) Will white CC et al. in 2014 did an critical illegal experiment by exposing nanoscale aluminum, aluminum oxides, aluminum hydroxide and its soluble salts on human health sensitive parts and systematically reviewed potential health risks posed by pharmaceutical, occupational and consumer exposures and found skin discoloration, hormone disorder; hypercholesterolemia & high B.P. with abnormal face symptoms The present studies similar to previous done by same scientists team exhibited same symptoms. The same scientist's team also conducted an scientific experiment on a 80 years old man by inducing auto medicament of nanoAg where they observed epileptic fits in that old person on which experiment conducted.⁽²⁷⁾ Ema M et al. in 2010 conducted nanoteratogenic experiment and observed reproductive and developmental toxicity studies of manufactured nanomaterials exhibited morbid sequel in higher dose AgNO₃ solution repeated mouth bolus induction along with multi abdominal organ toxic sequel microscopically in middle dose. Still data are less on osteo malformation of the AgNO₃ compound on bone of vertebrates.⁽²⁸⁾

The existing scientific experiment was undertaken to thoroughly study the bone malformation effect of prenatum exposure of nano Ag colloid solution through multiple oral boluses application on developing skeleton of Swiss Albino mice embryos. Zhang QL et al in 2011 did study on in-vivo toxicity of nano-alumina on mice neurobehavioral profiles and the potential mechanisms and they got maximum success rates. Our team of expert on scientific experimentation saw same late calcification of back skull bones which corroborate with research done by Zhang QL et al..²⁹ The bonny disfigurement exhibited were in the shape of no ossified side and back skull bones. Hypo plasticity of maxilla and nose bones, abnormal side bending of body, bone lacunae and breeching, breeching in parts of innominate bone, no

coalition of parts and maximum evident of extended spaces between two ribs and other chest bone abnormalities of development were also highlighted during the time of the present experiment. Alizarin alcian combine bone staining which is absolutely not approachable up to caudal tail region to color the caudum. Obviously lots of data existing on small size nano silver toxicity from multiple consumer accessories, the recent ongoing experiment on teratogenic effect of bonny system of pregnant Swiss albino mice and their fetuses shows variety of anomalies which is predominant among several types of teratogenicity executed till today. N. Hadrup, H.R. Lam et al. in 2014 studied oral toxicity of silver ions, silver nanoparticles and colloidal silver and confronted late bone development; our research also reported the same.⁽³⁰⁾ K.S. Hougaard et al. in 2015 carried a perspective on the developmental toxicity of inhaled nanoparticles and M. Ema et al. in 2016 conducted study on developmental toxicity of engineered nanomaterials in rodents and also denoted hypoplasticity of jaw bone our study also reported the same. ^(31,32) Y. Nishimura, et al. in 2016 did an nano teratogenic experiment using zebrafish in systems toxicology for developmental toxicity testing congenital anomalies J. Seiffert et al. in 2016 found pulmonary teratogenic and developmental effects of inhalation of spark-generated silver nanoparticles in Brown-Norway and Sprague-Dawley rats respiratory system ; In our study hypoplasticity of jaw bones exhibited as either a middle flat face or a slender snout that can be comparable with the typical human eye, eye brow, chin, nose, lips, beard, mustache, hair, hair color, skin and skin color features i.e. a middle flat face associated with hypoplasticity of jaw bone. It can also be termed as a cleft nose or a vanished or completely absent philtrum with a cleft lip which is almost same as per studies revealed by Y. Nishimura, et al. in 2016 and J. Seiffert et al. in 2016 .^(33,34) So keeping views and reporting of other scientists our study can be comparable with other study. In fact our study also showed different type of limb defects also. As a final conclude the existing research study revealed bonny malformation effect through repeated oral bolus feed of synthesized nano Ag colloidal solution on pups of pregnant Swiss albino mice delivered by exteriorize of horns on 18th day of G.A. are the successive victims. The present study also indicates 8, 16, 24, 32mg/k.g. b.w. repeated oral bolus feed from 7-12days of gestational days in pups of Swiss albino mice have definitely violation and detrimental effect on bonny system & the intensity of teratogenicity is dose and size dependant along with quantity of bony tissue affected is also dose and size dependant.

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Conflict of interest

Author declares that neither there is conflict of interest nor there is difference in opinion.

REFERENCES

1. Ismail T, Lee HK, Kim C et al. (2019) Comparative analysis of the developmental toxicity in *Xenopus laevis* and *Danio rerio* induced by Al₂O₃ nanoparticle exposure. *Environ Toxicol Chem* 38(12):2672–268
2. Ema M, Kobayashi N, Naya M, et al. (2010) Reproductive and developmental toxicity studies of manufactured nanomaterials. *Reprod Toxicol* 30(3):343–352
3. Krewski D, Yokel RA, Nieboer E et al. (2007) Human health risk and teratogenicity assessment for aluminum, aluminum oxide and aluminum hydroxide nanoparticles. *J Toxicol Environ Health B* 10(Suppl 1):1–269
4. Krause B C, Kriegel FL, Rosenkranz D et al. (2020) Aluminum and aluminum oxide nanomaterials uptake after oral exposure - a comparative study[J]. *Sci Rep* 10(1)
5. Medici S, Peana M, Pelucelli A et al. (2021) An updated overview on metal nanoparticles toxicity. *Sem Cancer Biol*
6. Sadiq IM, Pakrashi S, Chandrasekaran N et al. (2011) Studies on toxicity of aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) nanoparticles to microalgae species: *Scenedesmus* sp. and *Chlorella* sp. *J Nanopart Res* 13(8):3287–3299
7. Hayes KL, Mui J, Song B et al. (2020) Effects, uptake, and translocation of aluminum oxide nanoparticles in lettuce: a comparison study to phytoxic aluminum ions. *Sci Total Environ* 719(137393):1-137393.10
8. N. Seltenrich in (2013) Nanosilver: weighing the risks and benefits *Environ. Health Perspect.*, 121 (7), pp. A220-A225
9. M.E. Vance, T. Kuiken, E.P. Vejerano et al. (2015) Nanotechnology in the real world: redeveloping the nanomaterial consumer products

inventory Beilstein J. Nanotechnol., 6, pp. 1769-1780

10.A. Lazareva, A.A. Keller (2014), Estimating potential life cycle releases of engineered Nanomaterials from wastewater treatment plants ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng., 2 (7), pp. 1656-1665

11.M. Gulumian, J. Verbeek, C. Andraos, et al. (2016) Systematic review of screening and surveillance programs to protect workers from Nanomaterials PLoS One, 11 (11), Article e0166071

12.K.S. Hougaard, L. Campagnolo, P. Chavatte et al. (2015) A perspective on the developmental toxicity of inhaled nanoparticles Reprod. Toxicol., 56, pp. 118-140

13.Schultz H et al.(1999.2015). Potassium Compounds. Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry. 7th ed New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons. Online Posting Date: a5 Jun 2000

14. Ema, M.; Okuda, H.; Gamo, et al. (2017) A Review of Reproductive and Developmental Toxicity of Silver Nanoparticles in Laboratory Animals. *Reprod. Toxicol.* 67, 149– 164, DOI: 10.1016/j.reprotox.2017.01.005

15.Tortella G. R., Rubilar O., Durán N. et al. (2020) Silver Nanoparticles: Toxicity in Model Organisms as an Overview of Its Hazard for Human Health and the Environment. *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 390, 121974, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2019.121974

16. Clemente Z., Castro V. L. S. S., Moura M. A. M. et al. (2014) Toxicity Assessment of TiO₂ Nanoparticles in Zebrafish Embryos under Different Exposure Conditions. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 147, 129– 139, DOI: 10.1016/j.aquatox.2013.12.024

17.Charles, S., Jomini, S., Fessard, V., et al. (2018) Assessment of the in Vitro Genotoxicity of TiO₂ Nanoparticles in a Regulatory Context. *Nanotoxicology* 2018, 12, 357– 374, DOI: 10.1080/17435390.1451567

18.Rodriguez-Garraus A., Azqueta A., Vettorazzi A., et al. (2020) Genotoxicity of Silver Nanoparticles. *Nanomaterials*, 10, 251, DOI: 10.3390/nano10020251

19.Guo X., Li Y., Yan J. et al. (2016) Size-and Coating-Dependent Cytotoxicity and Genotoxicity of Silver Nanoparticles Evaluated Using in Vitro Standard Assays. *Nanotoxicology*, 10, 1373– 1384, DOI: 10.1080/17435390.2016.1214764

20.Li Y., Qin T., Ingle T. et al. (2017) Differential Genotoxicity Mechanisms of Silver Nanoparticles and Silver Ions. *Arch. Toxicol.*, 91, 509– 519, DOI: 10.1007/s00204-016-1730-y

21.Grodzik M., Sawosz E. (2006) The Influence of Silver Nanoparticles on Chicken Embryo Development and Bursa of Fabricius Morphology. *J. Anim. Feed Sci.*, 15, 111– 114, DOI: 10.22358/jafs/70155/2006

22.Patel S., Jana S., Chetty R. et al. (2018) TiO₂ Nanoparticles Induce Omphalocele in Chicken Embryo by Disrupting Wnt Signaling Pathway. *Sci. Rep.* 2018, 8, 4756, DOI: 10.1038/s41598-018-23215-7

23.Egloff C., Crump D., Chiu S. et al.(2011) In Vitro and in Ovo Effects of Four Brominated Flame Retardants on Toxicity and Hepatic mRNA Expression in Chicken Embryos. *Toxicol. Lett.*, 207, 25– 33, DOI: 10.1016/j.toxlet.2011.08.015

24.Chwalibog A., Sawosz E., Jaworski S et al. (2014) Toxicity of Pristine Graphene in Experiments in a Chicken Embryo Model. *Int. J. Nanomed.*, 9, 3913– 3922, DOI: 10.2147/ijn.s65633

25. Ghimire S., Zhang X., Zhang J. et al. (2022) Use of Chicken Embryo Model in Toxicity Studies of Endocrine-Disrupting Chemicals and Nanoparticles. *Chem. Res. Toxicol.*, 35, 550, DOI: 10.1021/acs.chemrestox.1c00399

26.Jomini S., Labille J., Bauda P. et al. (2012) Modifications of the Bacterial Reverse Mutation Test Reveals Mutagenicity of TiO₂ Nanoparticles and Byproducts from a Sunscreen TiO₂-Based Nanocomposite. *Toxicol. Lett.*, 215, 54– 61, DOI: 10.1016/j.toxlet.2012.09.012

27.Willhite CC, Karyakina NA, Yokel RA et al. (2014) Systematic review of potential health risks

- posed by pharmaceutical, occupational and consumer exposures to metallic and nanoscale aluminum, aluminum oxides, aluminum hydroxide and its soluble salts. *Crit Rev Toxicol* 44(S4):1–80
28. Ema M, Kobayashi N, Naya M et al. (2010) Reproductive and developmental toxicity studies of manufactured nanomaterials. *Reprod Toxicol* 30(3):343–352
29. Zhang QL, Li MQ, Ji JW, et al. (2011) In vivo toxicity of nano-alumina on mice neurobehavioral profiles and the potential mechanisms. *Int J Immunopathol Pharmacol* 24(1 Suppl):23S-29S
30. N. Hadrup, H.R. Lam (2014) Oral toxicity of silver ions, silver nanoparticles and colloidal silver-a review *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol.*, 68 (1) , pp. 1-7
31. K.S. Hougaard, L. Campagnolo, P. Chavatte-Palmer et al. (2015) A perspective on the developmental toxicity of inhaled nanoparticles *Reprod. Toxicol.*, 56 , pp. 118-140
32. M. Ema, M. Gamo, K. Honda et al. (2016) Developmental toxicity of engineered nanomaterials in rodents *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.*, 299 , pp. 47-52
33. Y. Nishimura, A. Inoue, S. Sasagawa, J et al. (2016) Using zebrafish in systems toxicology for developmental toxicity testing *Congenit. Anom. (Kyoto)*, 56 (1), pp. 18-27
34. J. Seiffert, A. Buckley, B. Leo, et al. (2016) Pulmonary effects of inhalation of spark-generated silver nanoparticles in Brown-Norway and Sprague-Dawley rats *Respir. Res.*, 17 (1), p. 85
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